

The Impact of Multinationalism and Solvency on Profitability ...

The Impact of Multinationalism and Solvency on Profitability of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) Multinational Enterprises

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Abstract

The current study examined the impact of multinationality and solvency on the profitability of multinational firms. In this study, a panel framework of forty-five FMCG has drawn from 2005 to 2017. This study adopted the dynamic generalized method of moments (GMM) and used the simultaneous equation method to cope with endogeneity issues and robustness result. Most of studies have formulated on large heterogeneous firms in literature and contained dummy variables, which are also causes of endogeneity. Hence in this study, large likely homogeneous firms have been used as samples. The results of this study suggest that solvency has a profound effect on performance. In this study, FMCGs showed inverse influence of multinationality on profitability. We concluded that the large FMCGs are at an optimum level of multinationality. So, if they would further increase cross-border investments, they could decrease their return on a total investment of assets.

Keywords: Financing Policy, Profitability, Multinationality, Generalized Method of Moments, FMCGs sector.

JEL Code: G32, L25, F23, C33, L66

1. INTRODUCTION

Corporate profitability is important and necessary for a company (Nanda & Panda, 2018). Firms realized the need to internationalize their business activities long ago as internationalization would have helped them to achieve huge credible profits at a moderate value. After making an appearance in modern literature on corporate profitability, the

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corporate structure has earned a significant value in terms of the international businesses and financing international operations. Surprisingly, Multinational Corporations (MNCs) have good fortune because they obtained the viewpoint of leadership at global markets in the closing of the 20th century (Bereznoy, 2017). Confidently, these firms were anticipating a slightly long-term future, but today this optimism throw is brittle. The life expectancy of a massive corporation is assumed to be short as this is a basic part of the global trade establishment in socioeconomic form.² The emerging needs of multinationals have emphasized the modernization of traditional corporate strategic management. It would ultimately improve modern corporate planning and disprove the global risk of the unsettled trade environment. So, there is a need to explore the influence of multinational trade on the profitability of firms. Thus, firms would surpass their strategy for investment decisions. Hennart (2007) reviewed the cost reduction argument in which firms have the authority to widen fixed costs above the significant market by international diversification. There are two approaches for the concept of Multinationals' profitability (Hennart, 2007). One is MNCs seek to expand globally because it reduces business risk. Here, it means MNCs have several countries affiliated to reduce their risk at a similar return range. Another is MNCs seek to expand internationally only because of profit. It means MNCs have several countries affiliated to increase their profitability.² Extensive studies have taken place on the importance of strategies regarding financial decisions and their effects on profitability. Solvency measured the strength of a firm because it relates long-term financial commitment with attainable debt and stock (Jagirani et al., 2016). The history of business shows that the success of business enterprises depends on the bright management of corporate finance. Corporate finance is differentiated into three main aspects, mainly on developing capital budgeting, capital structure, dividend policy, and working capital management (Supatanakornkij, 2015). The first two aspects can be associated with long-term capital, while others are concerned with the short-term capital. Moreover, in an organization's financing decisions, the capital structure is a principal part of adjusting the organization's financial mix. The significance of capital structure can be observed from two levels (Cheng, 2015). At the first micro-level, the significance of capital structure can be spotted from how the firm can draw the interest of raising funds from different financial sources. It is one of the crucial decisions for the business continuation and future growth potential.¹ Capital structure examines debt and equity commitments. It constructively introduces the cost of financial decisions and an outline of risk. At the second macro-level, all-inclusive can alter the business and economic environment that may affect an organization's capital structure. Therefore, the significance of solvency can be realized through the optimal debt ratio. The evaluation of solvency management can assist financial managers and policymakers in making better decisions for an organization (Ahmed & Abdullah, 2011). Worthy policies restrain firms from financially distressed conditions due to a high level of leverage. The capital structure is accepted as a firm resource in creating funds because planning the most appropriate capital structure is crucial for maximizing the profitability of a firm. Therefore, literature review signifies a positive association between determinates of solvency and profitability. Significant literature is present on corporate finance structure in a particular area. Still, empirical research mainly focuses on the small, medium, and large-sized trade firms. These firms are mostly single or combined within financial and non-financial sectors. That is why they did not give unique

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regulations and characteristics in a similar region. The empirical literature on the FMCGsⁱ sector is narrow; however, none of the research is available to examine the current years of the corporate structure of FMCGs. The previous literature measured different sectors, combined on heterogeneous firms by using simple panel regression methods with heterogeneity issues. The current study is an effort to contribute empirically and theoretically in terms of examining the impact of multinationality and proposing this missing link in the literature. In this study, we establish a global effect of Multinationality and solvency on the profitability of the FMCGs sector based on the GMM method. The FMCG market contains high competition with low costs (Carstea et al., 2017). These firms need more capital to alternate over time because these multinational firms are working globally through their subsidiary network. The global market of FMCGs is estimated to hold out \$15361.8 billions in 2025 and grow at a rate of 5.4% from 2018 to 2025 (Allied Market Research, 2019).

2. GAP OF THE STUDY

Several pieces of research empirically examined the relationship of profitability determinants with specific factors of industrial sectors in both developed and developing economies. However, most of the studies focused on investigating profitability by testing existing theories using diverse methods, examining the impact of firm-specific factors and micro and macroeconomic indicators. Conventionally, corporate finance literature centered around those firms, which worked in a single country, with country variation, as well as different heterogeneous companies. Wintokia, Linck, and Netter (2012) stated that the framework of corporate finance has shown the principle issue of endogeneity in their parameters. This issue can be resolved through exogeneity assumption, i.e., exogenous instruments. According to them, the current observations of explanatory parameters contain entirely individualistic past values of the dependent variable (profitability). Most assumptions gave distinct results that affect firm's strategic decisions making. Hence in the corporate finance literature, the latest view on international trade can be generated to bring a unique understanding of decision-making. So, previous research findings revealed a lack of harmony among the theories, determinants, methodologies, and firm-specific factors. Despite these studies, there is scant literature that empirically furnishes conclusive results on solvency and multinationality because the decisions of capital structure are dynamic. The scarcity of this literature is more critical for cross-industry differences. Cheng (2015) found evidence that financial decisions have different biases on account of cross-industry differences regarding industrial characteristics, and business risk. Although Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) enterprises have seen rapid growth in recent years despite challenging conditions, this success is because of mergers and acquisitions of these enterprises. This research would add literature to financial decision-making for both the global business and multinational FMCG sector.

2. Literature Review

Due to the greater importance of profitability, a large amount of literature has focused on factors that regulate the profitability of firms. Therefore, various types of industries are investigated by an abundant number of determinants and studies found diversified results according to the nature of industry (Jafari & Samman, 2015). However, most of the research

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scholars contributed mixed results. Moreover, literature from previous research on international business has concentrated on the locus of economies and the combination of country differences in relevance to production and agent financing (Foley & Manova, 2014). Further, firm heterogeneity has emerged in association with fixed and varying trade costs. The essence of financial decisions is to secure the fair composition of funding resources from which the firm can generate more return without hindering the interest of stakeholders. When a manager wants to raise capital externally, it makes the cost of information asymmetries and significance struggle.

2.1. Theories of Corporate Finance

The financial decision is to secure the fair composition of funding resources from which firms can generate more returns without hindering the interest of stakeholders. The analytical decisions could be taken by the managers for the stable survival of companies. So, the capital structure is one of the most demanding and compact decisions faced by companies (Pouraghajan et al., 2012). Therefore, it can be concluded that the most crucial cause of the firm's collapse is unsystematic, insufficient, and unsuitable financing and investment. Financial managers can also lower the cost of capital through appropriate decision-making. Hence, a firm source makes the resources of corporate assets. Capital structure is a combination of debt and equity. Distinct firms have unique capital structures. Even so, these financial resources construct on two fragments of investment policies (Pouraghajan et al., 2012). One is internal financial resources in which firms can finance through collected earnings, and the other is external financial resources in which firms can finance through debt and stock.

Further, influence of globalization activity and day to day advancements in technology have a greater influence on adjusting multinational operations and financial decision making (Raykov, 2017). So, financial management controls factors to determine the strength of the firm's solvency and conclusively safeguard owner's capital in changing environment. In the financing hierarchy, Myers (2003) pointed out that a few adaptations of agency theory implied pecking order as agency cost of equity. According to Cheng (2015), the theory reveals that managers have a great interpretation than investors. They take funding decisions as situational into a description of internal funds. In an era of globalization, corporate governance reviews some changes in economic policies, financial markets, investment opportunities, and financing choices due to tempting importance on the capital markets dependence (Nasimi, 2016). In literature, the beginning momentum for the relationship between multinationality and profitability approaches the theory of portfolio diversification (Hennart, 2007).

The solvency of a firm is considered standard performance because the firm can attain operational sustainability by meeting its short and long-term obligations (Ramin et al., 2017). More capital is required if corporate governance wants to increase their business and have higher gains. For that purpose, resources come from two principal sources that can classify as debt and equity capital. Siraj et al. (2019) examined that large extending firms have improved revenue by efficiently managing their assets. The essential factor of financial strategy is capital used in the victorious range. For the survival of any business, profitability can reinvest into the business (Sultan & Adam, 2015). So, the capital structure of any firm is

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placed in structure, processes, and mechanism that can guarantee the firm that managed in a way, to enhanced long-term equity value through reporting of managers and increasing firm profit (Rajendran & Nimalthasan, 2013).

Researchers have measured the complexity of firm financing. Myers (1984) examined two approaches on corporate debt. One is the Trade-off theory. It asserts that firms use debt to balance tax savings in opposition to the deadweight of bankruptcy costs. The second is the pecking order theory. It declares that given dire selection, firms first use retained earnings than debt and in utmost conditions use equity for financing. These approaches have two ideal suggestions. The first key indicates that leverage can manifest target amendment. So, the fluctuation can uniformly remove these targets. The second key implicates an inflexible structure of financing. Myers (2001) stated that firms follow the Pecking order theory when firms have a low internal cash flow to fund capital expenditure. Because of that firm would borrow first to finance expenditures rather than issue equity. Frank & Goyal (2008) showed that leverage demonstrates target adjustment because it is non-essentially stabilizing tax reduction in opposition to insolvency cost for firms. Consequently, they viewed target adjustment as a distinct hypothesis. So they have used the phrase static trade-off theory for the postulation. This static leverage model is determined by main factors such as taxes and insolvency.

2.2 Relationship of Multinationality and Profitability

The profitability of a multinational arrangement takes an interesting turn when its relationship is examined keeping in view international trade. All the inferences in theoretical literature of the international business assert that multinationality positively influences profitability, but empirical research did not show consistent results (Borda et al., 2017; Hennart, 2007). The observed association found this relationship to be positive, negative, and U-shaped (Borda et al., 2017). The inconsistency between results can be classified commonly into two courses of research. One is the focal point on quantification usage, which means that the main argument represents mixed results due to the absence of valid measures. The other is an examination of theoretical substructure and formation of multinational & profitability relations. It means that the conflicting theory of the multinational & profitability relationship is developed. This theory asserts that these contradictory results can resolve harmony between the multinational & profitability relation by introducing a three-stage theory of international evolution. In the first stage, internationalization negatively affects performance because when a firm moves abroad, they feature obligations of foreignness and other costs such as instruction cost and upfront cost (Contractor et al., 2003). In the second stage, international diversification can allocate profits. Hence in multinationality cases like monopolistic superiority, reserve in the market, depletion risk, and information gained from the board all are utilized by the researcher to describe a positive slope in a part of the all-inclusive S association (Borda et al., 2017). In the third stage, uncontrolled multinationality has high progressive costs with low gradual profits. During this stage of internationalization, the reasoning of TCI theory is commonly utilized. So, firms incline in foreign markets with high power at the first step (Contractor, 2007). Although behind stages, the surrounding market declines their potential and further complications increase negative impacts on firm profitability.¹ Commonly, internationalization is better for firms. Therefore, we hypothesized

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that:

H1: The degree of Multinationality of FMCGs has a significant impact on the profitability of FMCGs.

2.3 Relationship between Solvency and Profitability

Thenmozhi (2020) stated that corporate solvency is the potentiality of a firm to encounter its long-term leverage and capital structure. Originating literature maintains a positive association between leverage and profitability based on the estimation of trade-off theory. The theoretical relationship is confirmed by Reinhard and Li (2010). High profitable firms should have more debt, as the threat of insolvency would be lesser, and tax defenses would be a treasure for firms (Frank & Goyal, 2015). Yet, based on the estimation of pecking order theory, there is an inverse association between profitability and leverage. The discovery of Nanda & Panda (2018), Matar & Eneizan (2018), and Kodongo et al. (2014) empirically established the inverse association of leverage and profitability. Since according to them, profitable firms should have less debt because they preferred internal financing over debt. These findings can also express the actuality of external financing costs because of insolvency costs and unsymmetrical information problems.

In the modern era, new ideas elevate in research studies. So, in the conventional trade-off model, the anticipated value of debt tax shields and costs of financial affliction determines debt between them. Both values depend on presumed future profitability, regardless of perceiving future profitability (Cheng, 2015). Xu (2012) displayed evidence that an increased projection of profitability correlated to the main profits of debt. This lower cost of financial hardship on the forecast of traditional trade-off theories would examine by large US manufacturing firms. Hence, we hypothesized that:

H2: There is a significant (positive) effect of solvency on the profitability of the Multinational (FMCGs).

3. Research Methodology

The sampling frame of this study collects from the FMCGs sector (includes Food, Fruit, and Meat, drinks, Dairy products, Bread and other baked goods, Toiletries e.g. toothpaste, deodorant, and Alcohol, tobacco

Confectionery based on revenue. This sample had published in 2018 (Consultancy. uk, 2018). In this study, the sample selection constructs with the possibility of data and the essence of business. Therefore, sample size was acquired from the population of the top fifty FMCG multinational firms as dropping five firms because of the unavailability of data. In this study trial, the processed data is analyzed through descriptive and inferential statistics and regression of the generalized method of moments (First-difference GMM). The Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) estimator is one method to solve the problem of endogenous regressors. Holtz-Eakin (1988) and Arellano & Bond (1991) proposed a dynamic GMM estimator for panel data. They suggest a model technique in which lagged values of the dependent variable are used as an explanatory variable. The lags of dependent and independent variables are also utilized as an instrument for the regressor. A further description is given by Verbeek (2012) and Baltagi (2008). According to them, the system of equations of the GMM estimator can regard as a simultaneous estimation for robust results.

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In this estimator, one equation is for each year, and utilizing diverse instruments in every equation and regulating the equal parameters across equations. In dynamic panel GMM estimation, a potential source of omitted variables biases would terminate by first differencing the equation. It removes the individual effects and is procured in opposition to non-stationary series (Fatoki, 2017).

Profitability

= Lagged Profitability_{it}

$$+ \alpha_i + \beta_1 Liquidity_{it} + \beta_2 Solvency_{it} + \beta_3 Multinationality_{it} + \beta_4 size_{it} + \beta_5 Growth + u_{it} \text{ eq1}$$

$$Y_{it} - Y_{i,t-1} = \delta(Y_{i,t-1} - Y_{i,t-2}) + \beta(X_{it} - X_{i,t-1}) + \alpha_i + \mu_{it} - \mu_{i,t-1} \text{ eq2}$$

In the equation, two Y represent the dependent variable and X represent an independent variable.

3.1 SOURCES OF ENDOGENEITY AND BIASES

This section highlights the conceptual framework regarding why biases arise when we apply static OLS, FE, and RE models to evaluate the relationship between firm performance and corporate finance. As proposed in prior literature on corporate finance, these biases are arising by endogeneity (Wintoki et al., 2012). Most researchers recognized two potential sources of endogeneity.¹ One is unobservable heterogeneity, and the other is simultaneity. One source of endogeneity rises from the practicability.² It means that current observational values of explanatory corporate governance variables become the function of past firm profitability.³ Frequently neglecting this source of endogeneity for assumption may have crucial issues. That is mainly correct since the complicity in recognizing exogenous instruments. So, in this study, we used dynamic GMM estimator for robust analysis.

3.2 Study of Variables

The prior literature comes up with several financial ratios that constitute the summary of indicators. The prime objective of this study concerns the impact of Multinationality, liquidity, and solvency on returns. Therefore, we assume variables into three groups' dependent variables, explanatory variables, and control variables. We select profitability as a dependent variable, liquidity, and solvency as explanatory variables. Control variables are growth rate, firm size, and multi-nationality. Computation of these variables is given below:

Table 3.1: Computation of Variables

No	Variables		Variables calculation
1	Return on Assets	ROA	Income before Interest and Tax /average total assets
2	Return on Equity	ROE	Net income/average shareholder equity
3	Current ratio	CR	Current assets / Current liabilities
4	Quick ratio	QR	(Cash and equivalents + Marketable securities + Accounts receivable) / Current liabilities
5	Cash ratio	CASHR	Cash and cash equivalent / Current liabilities
6	Cash Conversion Cycle	CCC	Collection period + Days to sale inventory - Days Payable period. Collection period ratio = Average account receivables /sales/365

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			Days to sale inventory ratio = Average inventory/cost of sales/365 Days Payable period ratio = Average payable/cost of sales/365
7	Debt ratio	DR	Total liabilities / Total assets
8	LONG Term Debt to Equity Ratio	LTDER	Long term debt /Shareholder equity
9	Time Interest coverage ratio	TIER	Income before Interest and Tax / Interest expense
10	Total Debt to Equity Ratio	TDER	Total Debt /Shareholder equity
11	Multi-nationality	MULTI	foreign sales / total sales
12	Growth rate	GR	(Current year N. Sales-Last year N. Sales) / Last year sales
13	Firm size	FS	Natural Logarithm of total assets

4. Results

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

According to Kothari's (2004) examination, descriptive statistics analysis with some important statistical measurement is developing to indicate tools, such as central tendency, measures of dispersion, allocation of asymmetry (skewness), and other measures from the raw data. So, they use to summarize research data statistically so that this calculates the relationship of concerned data.

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics of all study variables

Variables	Mean	Median	Max	Min	STD	JB
ROA	0.114708	0.102879	0.378523	-0.020051	0.064182	324.3685
ROE	-0.025796	0.163969	28.26752	-191.5556	8.058902	7278608.
CR	1.225384	1.132131	10.23760	0.081338	0.579944	238851.9
QR	0.670717	0.607208	2.039259	0.214074	0.291063	368.0428
CASHR	0.228717	0.175306	1.469040	0.009838	0.191710	2315.482
CCC	29.63940	33.53455	446.8867	-330.7693	103.1172	273.3326
DR	0.708057	0.599981	10.94482	0.276549	0.738873	231522.9
LTDER	1.575474	0.494083	383.5294	-142.4773	18.24987	2858281
TIER	17.80480	8.846154	253.8889	-0.693548	27.27019	13497.46
TDER	3.643027	1.466283	712.1176	-272.7727	35.51363	2137423.
MULTI	0.539583	0.551541	1.491750	0.029635	0.230471	5.437695
GR	0.057570	0.038092	2.084146	-0.671675	0.162327	73223.92
FS	19.15734	19.20752	21.67253	8.522603	1.263637	16908.36

Note: Max, Min, STD, and JB refer to maximum, minimum, standard deviation, and Jarque Berra normality test.

In this data set of the multinational FMCG sector, profitability ratios are measured by ROA and ROE. The average value of ROA is 11.4 percent, which shows, firms earned a

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net average income of 11.2% from total invested assets, and the standard deviation recorded at 0.064 indicates that data spread near to average value. The average amount of ROE is -2.57 percent which shows firms lost an average income of -2.57% from total invested equity, while the standard deviation recorded at 8.05 shows data spread (far) away from the average value. The average rate of CR is 1.225, which indicates; the amount of cash has generated from current assets after current. The average amount of CASHR indicates that the firms have an average available cash balance of 0.2287 for payments of current liabilities. The average value reveals that firms have an average of 0.6707 most liquid assets to retire their current liabilities. The average rate of CCC indicates that the average time taken from cash spending to cash recovery is approximately one month. During that Time Company needs to pursue other sources for funding their working capital. While the standard deviation recorded 103 days that shows data dispersed away from the average value. The multinational FMCG Solvency is measured by debt ratio, long debt to equity ratio, time interest earned ratio, and total debt to equity ratio. The average rate of DR indicates that multinational FMCG firms have higher liabilities than total assets. The average amount of LDER indicates that multinational FMCG firms have higher leverage (long-term debt) than their equity. The average rate of TIER indicates that multinational FMCG firms have higher earnings to pay off their interest payment on the debt. The average amount of TDER indicates that multinational FMCG firms have high debt than equity. The average value indicates that multinational FMCG firms have a significant growth rate. The average rate of MULTI indicates that firms have significant foreign sales.

4.2 STATIONARY TEST

Testing of unit root in panel is fairly current than testing of unit root in time series (Barreira & Rodrigues, 2005). An econometrics problem of panel data arises from various applications of time series practices, these problems or issues which are primary to panels such as unit root, spurious regressions, and co-integration. In the time-series dimension, when we add a cross-section dimension. It provides power in testing for co-integration and non-stationary. As long, this power is increasing due to the increase in the number of observations (Barreira & Rodrigues, 2005). Altogether, an increasing number of cross-sectional dimensions also drive current obstacles to new queries. Specifically, the entry of cross-section dependency, which can bias the outcomes of the panel unit root test in small trials (samples), these issues uniquely diminished by adding large cross-sectional and time-series dimensions.

Table 4.2-1 Represents Stationary Test of all variables which are run in E-views 10 software.

Method at level and equation individual intercept					individual intercept and trend			
Var.	LLC	IPS	ADF-FCs	PP-FCs	LLC	IPS	ADF-FCs	PP-FCs
ROA	-7.77 (0.0000)	-5.9770 (0.0000)	188.857 (0.0000)	241.212 (0.0000)	-10.7746 (0.0000)	-5.47487 (0.0000)	177.898 (0.0000)	272.550 (0.0000)
ROE	-6.8318 (0.00)	-6.3362 (0.0000)	203.661 (0.0000)	265.101 (0.0000)	-7.36360 (0.0000)	-4.05258 (0.0000)	165.833 (0.0000)	274.951 241.972
CR	-13.5325 (0.0000)	-8.45559 (0.0000)	225.287 (0.0000)	211.693 (0.0000)	-11.6219 (0.0000)	-5.57026 (0.0000)	181.685 (0.0000)	241.972 (0.0000)
QR	-8.34069 (0.0000)	-4.89756 (0.0000)	160.185 (0.0000)	165.281 (0.0000)	-9.85737 (0.0000)	-3.10441 (0.0010)	143.533 (0.0003)	219.682 (0.0000)

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CASHR	-9.72766 (0.0000)	-5.51562 (0.0000)	182.806 (0.0000)	182.469 (0.0000)	-11.9993 (0.0000)	-2.99561 (0.0016)	134.681 (0.0014)	160.522 (0.0000)
CCC	-12.0058 (0.0000)	-4.26246 (0.0000)	137.614 (0.0009)	125.753 (0.0077)	-7.55334 (0.0000)	-3.20178 (0.0007)	153.464 (0.0000)	143.544 (0.0003)
DR	-11.5600 (0.0000)	-4.76113 (0.0000)	164.295 (0.0000)	138.751 (0.0007)	-14.4241 (0.0000)	-3.66199 (0.0001)	142.424 (0.0004)	163.647 (0.0000)
LTDER	-5.43179 (0.0000)	-3.44693 (0.0000)	157.966 (0.0003)	137.011 (0.0010)	-6.76647 (0.0000)	-2.27701 (0.0114)	127.151 (0.0061)	134.164 (0.0018)
TIER	-2.57317 (0.0000)	-1.46012 (0.0721)	147.179 (0.0001)	157.319 (0.0000)	-7.44110 (0.0000)	-1.89488 (0.0291)	127.490 (0.0057)	146.563 (0.0002)
TDER	-17.5429 (0.0000)	-7.45740 (0.0000)	184.558 (0.0000)	153.683 (0.0000)	-20.1182 (0.0000)	-6.56240 (0.0000)	173.848 (0.0000)	173.633 (0.0000)
MULTI	-6.01336 (0.0000)	-1.29397 (0.0978)	114.449 (0.0420)	118.793 (0.0227)	-9.91870 (0.0000)	-0.98214 (0.1630)	105.699 (0.1236)	102.294 (0.1770)
GR	-14.3887 (0.0000)	-9.83292 (0.0000)	258.076 (0.0000)	284.542 (0.0000)	-17.0930 (0.0000)	-9.19487 (0.0000)	244.905 (0.0000)	320.049 (0.0000)
FS	-8.35335 (0.0000)	-4.56686 (0.0000)	168.854 (0.0000)	239.004 (0.0000)	-10.4787 (0.0000)	-4.26786 (0.0000)	153.753 (0.0000)	183.977 (0.0000)

Note: Upper values show t statistic and in parentheses, I mark Probability values. These values are calculated at Automatic lag length selection based on SIC: 0 to 1. According to t statistic, all variables are stationary at level but MULTI is non-stationary at individual intercept and trend.so I put the first difference to make it stationary.

4.2.1 Granger Causality Test

In economic relationships, the application of distributed lag models is to produce support about the direction of causality (Studenmund, 2017). Granger causality is a condition of estimating time series in which one variable continually and probably change before another variable so, Granger Causality analysis is used to estimate the time series comprised of a panel data that are correlated or how much time series “y” Granger cause “x” and vice-versa (Granger, 1969). According to this test we recognize which variable leads the other by bivariate regression.

Table no.4.2.2: Bidirectional relationship between dependent and independent variables, under total observations 495. In the Null Hypothesis column, the first-row shows INDV does not Granger Cause to DV, and the second row shows DV does not Granger Cause to INDV.

Variables	Null Hypothesis	F-Statistic	Prob.	Result
CR	CR to RA	0.19094	0.8262	Reject
	RA to CR	1.98210	0.1389	Reject
QR	QR to RA	1.82145	0.1629	Reject
	RA to QR	0.37514	0.6874	Reject
CASHR	CASHR to RA	2.25093	0.1064	Reject
	RA to CASHR	1.98210	0.1389	Reject
CCC	CCC to RA	3.75020	0.0242	Fail to Reject
	RA to CCC	1.47432	0.2299	Reject
DR	DR to RA	6.82761	0.0012	Fail to Reject
	RA to DR	0.69285	0.5006	Reject
LTDER	LDER to RA	1.94182	0.1445	Reject

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	RA to LDER	1.97559	0.1398	Reject
TIER	TIER to RA	0.11196	0.8941	Reject
	RA to TIER	0.41747	0.6589	Reject
TDER	TDER to RA	2.68912	0.0689	Reject
	RA to TDER	2.00390	0.1359	Reject
MULTI	MULTI to RA	0.11246	0.8937	Reject
	RA to MULTI	0.98956	0.3725	Reject
GR	GRTHR to RA	6.04366	0.0026	Fail to Reject
	RA to GRTHR	0.30234	0.7392	Reject
FS	FS to RA	4.18466	0.0158	Fail to Reject
	RA to FS	0.75706	0.4696	Reject

Note: CCC, DR, GR, and FS are showed Bivariate Relationship.

4.3 The Effect of Multinationality and Solvency on Profitability by Gmm (First-Difference)

Primarily we are looking at the specification tests of models, reported in table no: 4.2. The table shows that the Hansen test of (over-identification) J- statistic tests with probability value < 0.1, the null hypothesis that the instruments are valid cannot be rejected because all models contain the significant value of J- statistic greater than 10.0 (Chenge, 2015). These specified models have sustained the rule of thumb concerning instruments and groups as the instruments used in models is not greater than the number of groups. AR (1) and AR (2) test of first and second-order serial correlation, in which first-order serial correlation is allowed, but the second-order serial correlation is not allowed. So, we are describing the AR (2) test of all models, which shows that all models have no second-order serial correlation as to their probability value < 0.05, which represents that the models are correctly identified (Wintokia et al., 2012).

Table 4.3: Dynamic GMM Estimation, return on assets (ROA) as dependent variable.

IV	M(1)		M(2)		M(3)		M(4)	
	CF/(P)	S.E/t-S	CF/(P)	S.E/t-S	CF/(P)	S.E/t-S	CF/(P)	S.E/t-S
Δroa_{it-1}	0.3093 58 (0.0000)	0.0104 63 29.566 82	0.2902 62 (0.0000)	0.0085 68 33.878 96	0.2653 77 (0.0000)	0.0067 58 39.267 20	0.2640 61 (0.0000)	0.0068 2 38.674 2
CCC	- 0.0001 2 (0.0000)	2.46E- 05 - 5.1718 9						
QR							0.0126 11 (0.0000)	0.0028 0 4.5038 8
CR			0.0004 84	0.0023 42				

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			(0.8365)	0.2065 33				
CASH R					0.0173 27 (0.0000)	0.0038 69 4.4780 47		
DR					0.0119 07 (0.0000)	0.0028 30 4.2074 28		
LTDE R	0.0001 42 (0.0000)	3.33E- 05 4.2637 38						
TDER			6.73E- 05 (0.0003)	1.85E- 05 3.6337 54				
TIER							0.0005 36 (0.0000)	4.11E- 0 13.018 6
MULT I	- 0.0512 9 (0.0000)	0.0097 78 - 5.2460 0	- 0.0518 4 (0.0000)	0.0118 31 - 4.3823 81	- 0.0502 9 (0.0000)	0.0105 67 - 4.7594 2	- 0.0422 7 (0.0000)	0.0085 8 - 4.9241
FS	- 0.0049 6 (0.0528)	0.0025 57 - 1.9412 6	- 0.0043 4 (0.0944)	0.0025 96 - 1.6756 83	- 0.0069 1 (0.0001)	0.0017 74 - 3.8976 8	- 0.0072 9 (0.0000)	0.0015 2 - 4.8015
GR	0.0159 86 (0.0000)	0.0026 38 6.0593 66	0.0135 1 (0.0000)	0.0024 90 5.4287 17	0.0156 4 (0.0000)	0.0018 75 8.3423 1	0.0174 24 (0.0000)	0.0017 0 10.212 5
J-S	39.01872		39.42116		41.39630		40.49905	
P-J	0.469036		0.451044		0.366491		0.404024	
S.R	0.643526		0.639036		0.626473		0.590191	
INST	45		45		45		45	
AR1(P)	0.0987		0.8176		0.0118		0.0100	
AR2(P)	0.3172		0.9092		0.2652		0.4507	

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Obs	493	493	493	493
INS	@dynΔroa,-2, ΔCCC, ΔLTDER, ΔLTDER, ΔMULTI, ΔFS, ΔGR	@dynΔroa,-2, ΔCR, ΔTDER, ΔMULTI, ΔFS, ΔGR	@dynΔroa,-2, ΔCASHR, ΔDR, ΔMULTI, ΔFS, ΔGR	@dynΔroa,-2, ΔQR, ΔTEIR, ΔMULTI, ΔFS, ΔGR

Note: This table reveals the Dynamic GMM evaluation results of four equations, where ROA is the dependent variable, and others are explanatory variables in this table M1 used for model equation 1, CF for coefficient, P for probability value, SE for standards errors, t-S for statistic value, J-S for Hansen test of over-identification statistic value, P-J for probability value of Hansen test, INST for auto number of instruments used for transformation in the level equation, AR1 (P) and AR2 (P) for first & second-order serial correlation in the first-differenced residuals, Obs for the number of observation and INS for the instrument used in the level equation. In the level equation, we used all explanatory variables in the first difference form as an internal instrument, transformed them for infinity lagged formation.

4.4 Empirical Findings

The rate of adjustment concerns the superior level of profit. It means the influence of lagged performance on former periods in the current profitability (Cheng, 2015). The modification rate towards the level concerns the worth of adjustment and off-level. If the coefficient is positive under the unity, then the marked profitability is gained by firms. So the adaptation level of capital decisions has organized in a better form. According to this assumption, our empirical results determine a significant and positive association of lagged return on corporate financial decisions across all four models shown in Table.4.3. All coefficients are less than one, which indicates a dynamic financial decision for determining multinational firms because they are modifying their profitability to the expected level across time. In our empirical findings, the second insight, which estimates with solvency determinates of the firm, shows a significant positive relationship with return on assets but at a different significance level. It assures that these Multinational FMCGs are fundamentally borrowed largely and have more debt than their equity as a big steady, and recognized beneficial firms hold on large debt excluding investors risk (Frank & Goyal, 2015). The multinationality relation estimates that if these Multinational FMCGs would disperse more of their foreign sales, it will decrease in return on resources. These results support the research of Berry & Kaul (2016), and Borda et al. (2016), and Kircaa et al. (2016). The progressing section of estimated models in table no: 4.3 shows that each model contains solvency determinates gathered with the same control variables in all models. So, it would decrease the endogeneity issue in our models' estimation. The FS relation reveals that these Multinational FMCGs are negatively associated with the dispersion of their assets. If these firms disperse more, it decreased the returns. These results contradict the research of Bagh et al. (2016) and Arunkumar & Radharamanan (2011). The GR variable indicates a positive and statistically significant relationship with return on assets. It predicts that if these multinational firms enhance their sales, that would also increase their return on assets.

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5. Conclusion of Main Findings

FMCGs have significantly high leverage than other sectors firms. FMCGs are old, large multinationality, high business risks, free cash flows, foreign exchange risks, growth, debt tax shields, political risks, less profitability, bankruptcy risks, and more diversified than other corporations. In this study, the main finding of corporate finance is less certainty of liquidity management. It varies over the period, as described in mean distribution. FMCGs firms assist an association of their assets and liabilities. So it creates a sound effect on the profitability of firms. The return on assets shows that the FMCGs sector contains less return from their investment during the study period, despite that these firms have large cash invested in working capital. The liquidity position of FMCGs degenerated during the study period as liquidity variables did not reach the standard norms. So firms can enhance internal capital and increase their cash by internal cash generation process and reduce liabilities. It requires critical management practices that can assist the managers in developing the financial performance of their operation. The liquidity performance of FMCGs, overall, shows a good position. Subsequently, the FMCGs generate an appreciative impact of leverage on profitability. These findings imply that FMCGs produce greater returns from long-term funds and use more debt capital than equity capital because firms trade on equity advantages. This assumption supports the trade-off theory. This discussion reveals that leverage consumes efficiently. The Multinational-Profitability relationship plays various roles at different stages of multinationality (Kirca et al., 2016). According to the descriptive statistic of the study, FMCGs are mostly at the final stage of multinationality. The regression result shows that FMCGs give minor returns to overall firm value or further increase in multinationality decrease the financial return. These findings imply that recent Multinationality is critical for FMCGs to operate profitably in the diversification process because transaction cost problems often arise in these industries due to the transfer of sales/assets in foreign markets, as predicted by internalization theory. Thus, the principal assumption of internalization theory with empirical analysis of FMCGs layout is powerful insights about the role and nature of foreign sales to total sales in firm multinationality.

6. Policy Recommendation

The shortage of funds and struggle to capitalize on growing sectors especially is remarkable in the manufacturing area. The emerging fast-growing knowledge-based firms are afraid of funding schemes and capitalization from the financial system (Cheng 2015). The most prominent issue of growing a firm is how private investment takes out from the grey area to better diversification in products and sources. In the evolution of financial markets, these are the main problems. Hence, this study can consider beneficial for Shareholders, investors, policymakers, regulators, financial analysts, researchers, and managers because these large FMCGs firms contain all derivatives of the trade functions. Thus, in multinational firms, the aspects of business such as high insolvency, high competition, less return, risks, large business cycles, huge R&D cost, mergers and acquisitions, a network of foreign subsidiaries, and high power of

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uncertainties made them demanding to fund from not only from traditional financing channels, but they also use other large financial intermediaries. So, the multinational firm develops its strategy to maintain its administrative infrastructure and organizational capabilities through drawing a network of foreign subsidiaries overseas in an economically modern area like Europe and developing regions such as Latin America (Mendoza et al., 2019).

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APPENDIX**Table 1: List of all study samples of Multinational FMCGs firms**

No	Companies	Location	No	Companies	Location	No	Companies	Location
3	P&G	U.S	23	AB InBev	Belgium U.K	41	Asahi breweries	Japan
4	Tyson food	U.S	24	Unilever	London U.K	42	Japan Tobacco	Japan
5	Coca-Cola	U.S	25	British A.T	London U.K	43	Kirin Brewery Company	Japan
6	Colgate Palmolive	U.S	26	Diageo	London U.K	44	Shiseido	Japan
7	Johnson & Johnson	U.S	27	Danone	France	45	Suntory	Japan
8	Kellogg	U.S	28	Imperial Tobacco	England U.K			
9	PepsiCo	U.S	29	Essity	Sweden			
10	Philip Morris	U.S	30	Reckitt Benckiser	England U.K			
11	Group bimbo	U.S	31	Pernod Ricard	France			
12	Campbell	U.S	32	LVMH	France U.K			

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13	Kraft Heinz	U.S	33	Carlsberg	Denmark			
14	Molson Coors	U.S	34	Henkel	Germany			
15	Mondelez	U.S	35	Bunge food	Netherland U.K			
16	Kimberly Clarak	U.S	36	Royal Friesland Campin	Netherland U.K			
17	Estée Lauder	U.S	37	Danish crown	Denmark U.k			
18	Hormel food	U.S	38	Arla Food	Denmark			
19	Kao	Japan	39	Nestle	Switzerland			
20	Nippon meat packers	Japan	40	BRF Brasil Foods	Brazil			

¹ Fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) are the largest group of products, which consumes in the daily life of humans. These consumer products commonly utilize by the clause of society and FMCGs are recognized as a common contributor to the economy because the population spends a significant amount of their income on these products. FMCGs products have a quick turnover because they are frequently purchased.